

COMBATING CYBERBULLYING: THE ISSUE OF RESPONSIBILITY IN PROTECTING CHILDREN FROM HARMFUL INFORMATION

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Abstract:

This article is dedicated to cyber threats and responsibility in protecting children from harmful information. With the widespread use of the Internet and social networks, the problem of cyberbullying is becoming relevant and poses a serious threat to the psychological health and safety of young people. The article examines the characteristics of cyberbullying, its impact on children, and methods of combating it. The issue of accountability is analyzed from the perspective of the role of parents, teachers, social platforms, and government bodies. The importance of legislation, education, and technological solutions in protecting children from harmful information is emphasized.

Keywords: cyberbullying, child protection, harmful information, internet security, responsibility, social networks, psychological impact, legality, education, technological solutions.

The issue of protecting children from information that negatively affects their health is currently recognized as one of the most pressing socio-cultural problems not only at the national, but also at the global level. Studies show that [1] more than 50 percent of minors are victims of cyberbullying, and these figures may increase as the number of Internet users increases. Also, some adults are vulnerable to online threats.

Along with the development of information and communication technologies, forms of hooliganism are also changing, moving beyond the boundaries of traditional spaces to digital platforms. At one time, children could at least be in a safe environment in their own homes. Today, cyberbullies have the opportunity to influence victims 24 hours a day, every day of the week - through social networks, messaging services, email, and online games.

The negative consequences of this situation are profound and multifaceted, leading to severe psychological, emotional, and even physical trauma in children. Therefore, protecting children from the flow of negative information and developing comprehensive preventive measures against cyberbullying remains one of the priorities of modern social policy.

Today, a number of consistent and effective measures are being implemented in our country to protect children from the negative influence of information. In particular, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Protection of Children from Information Harmful to Their Health" [2] is one of the main regulatory legal acts defining the legal basis in this area. This law serves as an important tool for preventing psychological, mental, and moral violence against children in the information space, ensuring their mental and emotional health, and forming a healthy information environment.

Its influence on the prevention of violence manifests itself in the following main areas:

firstly, the law provides legal restrictions against content that promotes information-based violence - including threats, harassment, disrespect, and psychological pressure.

secondly, Articles 1 and 4 establish clear rules for ensuring the information security of children, aimed at reducing the impact of negative information on the Internet and in the media.

thirdly, Article 6 provides a clear definition of negative information, such as violence, antisocial behavior, and suicide. This allows you to filter and restrict the promotion of threatening content.

Fourthly, Categorizing information products into categories such as 12+, 16+, 18+ allows for the selection of content that is appropriate for children's age psychology and does not harm their health.

fifthly, Article 7 establishes the responsibility of parents, educational institutions, and authorized bodies for ensuring the information security of the child. This strengthens the role of the family and the education system in prevention.

Sixthly, The Law serves to institutionalize preventive work in the prevention of information threats, that is, to carry out preventive work on a systematic and cooperative basis.

ethirdly, This Law assigns specific powers to the Ministry of Culture and Tourism, the Mahalla and Family, the Ministry of Internal Affairs, and other relevant authorities, which are institutional guarantees at the state level for the protection of children from information abuse.

As can be seen from the analysis of the above-mentioned legal documents, ensuring information security is an important preventive direction aimed at eliminating the root causes of violence against children. This law, adopted in Uzbekistan, complies with international legal standards in this area and serves as an effective preventive tool for the early prevention of information abuse.

However, in our view, one of the main criteria determining the degree of effectiveness of any normative legal act is the mechanism of its implementation and the established liability measures for non-compliance with it. In particular, the adoption of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which is being analyzed above, means that a legal basis has been created in this area, however, it would be incorrect to conclude that the existence of this law fully protects children from information abuse.

The effective functioning of the law depends, first of all, on the presence of clearly and firmly established liability measures for its violation. Unfortunately, although almost eight years have passed since the adoption of this law, specific criminal or administrative liability measures for violating its requirements have not yet been expressed through specific legal norms. This means that there is a systemic gap in the full provision of the law's law enforcement function.

In this regard, the experience of some foreign countries, including the legislation of the Russian Federation and the Republic of Kazakhstan, is distinguished by the presence of strong administrative and legal mechanisms for the protection of children from information abuse.

In particular, Article 6.17 of the Code of the Russian Federation on Administrative Responsibility^[3] establishes specific measures of administrative responsibility for offenses related to the distribution, storage, and use of information products harmful to the health and development of children. According to it, citizens who violate the established requirements for the distribution of information products are fined from two to three thousand rubles, officials - from five to ten thousand rubles, persons engaged in entrepreneurial activity - from five to ten thousand rubles with confiscation of products or suspension of activities for up to ninety days, and legal entities - from twenty to fifty thousand rubles with temporary suspension of activities or confiscation of products.

Also, the second part of the article establishes requirements for taking special administrative and technical measures in places where children can use information disseminated via the Internet and telecommunication networks, and in cases of non-compliance with them, similar sanctions are provided.

Part three of the article establishes liability for the distribution of advertisements for involving children in the production of information products harmful to the health and

development of children. According to it, citizens will be fined from one thousand to one and a half thousand rubles, officials - from two thousand to three thousand rubles, and legal entities - from twenty thousand to thirty thousand rubles.

The legal measures taken in the Republic of Kazakhstan to protect children from informational abuse are also noteworthy for their high effectiveness. In particular, Article 156-1 of the Code of the Republic of Kazakhstan on Administrative Responsibility [4] establishes liability measures for the dissemination of information that negatively affects the health and development of children in the information environment.

This article defines the following acts as offenses:

Distribution of periodicals without the age category mark;

dissemination through the air of information products marked "from 18 years of age," not at a specified time;

Distribution of information products through television and radio programs without the definition of an age category, i.e., violation of the requirement to indicate an age-appropriate recommendation at the beginning of the content or after a break.

When these cases occur for the first time, a warning measure is applied. At the same time, the distribution of audiovisual or printed information products without specifying the age category also entails special liability.

The most important thing is that if these offenses are committed repeatedly within a year, the sanctions in the article become more serious:

For individuals - in the amount of 20 monthly calculation indices,

for small business entities or non-profit organizations - 50 calculated indicators,

For medium-sized businesses - 60 calculated indicators,

For large business entities, an administrative fine of 200 calculated indicators is established.

The above-mentioned legal approaches show that not only preventive, but also effective law enforcement measures have been established to ensure the safety of children in the information environment. It can be said that this experience will serve to improve the legislation of Uzbekistan, in particular, to strengthen the enforcement mechanism of the Law "On the Protection of Children from Information Harmful to Their Health."

From this point of view, in order to ensure the information security of children and strengthen the implementation of legislation on their protection from information that causes moral, psychological and spiritual harm, it is advisable to introduce a special article 597 "Violation of legislation on the protection of children from information harmful to their health and development" into the Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Administrative Responsibility. This norm will serve to legally guarantee the safety of children in the information space, strengthen preventive control, and further increase responsibility in this area.

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